

**APPENDIX 3B: MEASURING EFFECTS OF LEARNING RESOURCES AND
PROCESS EVALUATION
RESEARCH PARTICIPANT ASSENT FORM-STUDENTS**

Research project: Development and testing of digital learning resources for informed health choices and participation in informed dialogues about health in Rwanda (CHOICE PROJECT)

1. INTRODUCTION

We are doing a research study about how people can be helped to understand and assess information that concerns their health. A research study is a way to learn more about people, how they live their lives and how they make decisions about their lives and what happens to them when they make decisions.

We are asking you to participate in this study because we think that your contribution will help us develop materials that can help children like you understand and assess information about their health.

First of all, there are some things about this study you should know.

Participation in this study is purely voluntary and you may feel free not to join or to stop participating if you feel uncomfortable with the study activities at any time after joining. Your parents/guardians know about this study. If you do not want to be in this research study, you will not be penalized.

If you decide that you want to be part of this study, your teacher will teach you some concepts needed to make informed health choices. During this time, we will give you some of the materials we have developed and then ask you some questions (claim questions). We may ask you to provide comments and feedback in form of focus group discussions and interviews to gather users' experience of using resources.

2. BENEFITS TO YOU

There will be no direct benefits to you but we think that by participating in this study, you will receive free health information.

3. POSSIBLE RISKS TO YOU

We do not anticipate the study to cause you any harm, risks or dangers. We do not think that your school performance will be affected by participating in this research.

4. CONFIDENTIALITY

If you choose to participate all the information you give us will be kept as a secret and it will not bear your name or your parent/guardian's name. When we are finished with this study we will write a report about what was learned. This report will not include your name or that you were in the study. If you have understood everything about the study and all your questions have been answered, and you decide you want to be in this study, please sign your name below. On the other hand, if you don't want to be in the

study there is no problem, don't sign this paper. Signing below means that you have understood, and you are willing to join the study.

5. CONSENT TO THE USE OF VIDEO AND PHOTOS FOR THE INFORMED HEALTH CHOICES PROJECT

We would like to use video and photos to help people learn about the project and learning resources. They will be used in learning resources, on the project website; in presentations at meetings and conferences; in scientific journals; in the news media; and in social media, such as Twitter and Facebook. If you sign this form, you give us permission to use the video and/or photos of you and you can revoke (take back) your permission to use the video and/or photos, but this will only apply to future use, meaning the videos and/or photos will not be removed where they have already been used. This form will be kept securely by the project, but it may be shared with others who wish to use the videos or photos, for example scientific journals.

Study Participant

Your signature: _____ Date _____

Your name: _____ Date _____

Study Participant consent to use your video and/or photo in the project

Your signature: _____ Date _____

Staff obtaining assent

Signature of person obtaining assent: _____ Date _____

Printed name of person obtaining assent: _____ Date _____

Witness

Signature of Witness: _____ Date _____

Printed name of Witness: _____ Date _____